

Mercury Acetamide as a Mercurating Agent.

BY K. G. NAIK AND L. D. SHAH.

The mercuration of organic compounds has been studied by a number of workers (Dimorth, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2154 ; 1899, **32**, 758 ; 1902, **35**, 2044 ; Schoeller and Scrauth, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 2089 ; 1909, **42**, 778 ; Hoffmann, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 1904 ; 1900, **33**, 1328 ; Petterson, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1912, **86**, 458, etc.). The most commonly employed reagents are mercuric oxide and the acetate but mercury acetamide has seldom been used for the purpose. The only isolated instance where mercury acetamide is used as a mercurating agent is its action on methyl methylmalonate (Schoeller and Scrauth *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 784).

From the experiments recorded herein, it appears that mercury acetamide can be employed as fruitfully as the acetate for the preparation of organomercury compounds. Thus the substances enumerated below, *viz.*, (1) cyanacet-methylamide, (2) cyanacet-ethylamide, (3) cyanacet-propylamide, (4) cyanacet-butylamide, (5) cyanacet-isobutylamide, (6) cyanacet-amylamide, (7) cyanacet-isohexylamide, (8) cyanacet-heptylamide, (9) ethyl cyanoacetate, (10) cyanoacetamide, (11) cyanoacetanilide, (12) cyanacet-*m*-toluidide, (13) cyanacet-*o*-toluidide, (14) cyanacet-*p*-toluidide, (15) cyanacet-benzylamide, (16) cyanacet- α -naphthylamide, (17) cyanacet- β -naphthylamide, (18) cyanacet-1:3:4-xylidide, (19) cyanacet-1:4:5-xylidide are all attacked by mercury acetamide, one of the hydrogens of the reactive methylene group being replaced by the hydroxymercuri ($-\text{HgOH}$) group.

The properties of the compounds indicate the presence of a very weak C—Hg bond such as is always found when the carbon involved is in the α -position to a -CO-group. Thus they are readily decomposed by hot 0.25N-hydrochloric acid. Hydrogen sulphide, ammonium sulphide or sodium sulphide causes the formation of black mercuric sulphide. Potassium iodide ruptures the C—Hg linkage with the consequent formation of alkali hydroxide. Phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate are found to liberate metallic mercury.

The general constitution assigned to the above compounds follows from the considerations given below:—

1. That the mercury atom has not replaced the hydrogen atom of the aromatic nucleus because—

(a) Cyanacet-methylamide which does not contain such a nucleus forms a similar hydroxymercuri-derivative.

(b) A study of the known mercury compounds shows that the nuclear mercury atom is not decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid (0.25N) (*cf.* Scrauth and Baur Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2740), whereas hydroxymercuricyanacetanilide is decomposed by hot 0.25N-hydrochloric acid.

2. That the mercury atom has not replaced the hydrogen attached to the nitrogen atom of the —NHR group, for—

(a) Ethyl cyanoacetate, which does not contain such a hydrogen, forms a similar mono-mercurated product with mercury acetamide.

(b) The properties of the compounds suggest a carbon-mercury rather than a nitrogen-mercury linkage, because, whereas all the N—Hg compounds are decomposed by *cold* dilute acid (*cf.* Ley and Kissel, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1357) the compounds described herein are decomposed by *hot* dilute acids only.

3. That the mercury atom has not entered the aliphatic part of the amido-group, because—

(a) Cyanoacetamide which does not contain such an aliphatic part forms a similar hydroxymercuri-compound.

4. That the mercury atom is directly attached to the carbon atom of the methylene group, for—

(a) Hydroxymercuricyanacet benzylamide gives monobromocyanacet-benzylamide on treatment with bromine in aqueous suspension.

(b) The properties and behaviour of the compounds obtained herein exactly correspond with those having mercury in the α -position to a keto or a phenyl group which renders the α -mercury atom unusually reactive.

Cyanoacetamide reacts with mercury acetamide in aqueous or alcoholic solution giving hydroxymercuricyanoacetamide, which is formulated as $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{HgOH})\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$. This constitution has been assigned to the compound on the ground that on treatment with bromine in aqueous suspension it gives dibromocyanacetamide which

is identical with the one obtained by Hesse (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, **18**, 735) by the direct bromination of cyanoacetamide.

Petterson (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1912, *ii*, **86**, 458) obtained from mercuric acetate and ethyl cyanoacetate, hydroxymercuricyanoacetic ester, $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{HgOH})\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$. Probably an acetoxy-mercury derivative is first formed which subsequently undergoes hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. Mercury acetamide also reacts with ethyl cyanoacetate giving a quantitative yield of the hydroxymercuri-derivative. In all probability an acetamido-derivative is first formed which then undergoes hydrolysis as represented below:—

The formation of the same product from mercuric acetate and mercury acetamide naturally raises the question as to the constitution of the latter. Ley and Kissel (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 1357) deduced from the low electrical conductivity of mercury acetamide that it contains an N—Hg bond. It is well-known that, in order that a mercuric salt may react with an aromatic organic compound it must be capable of hydrolytic dissociation. Hence it may be that during the reaction between mercury acetamide and substituted cyanoacetamides, the former may react in the tautomeric form (II) containing the O—Hg linkage.

The latter form is susceptible to hydrolytic dissociation, since all mercuric salts of oxyacids are considerably hydrolysed in aqueous solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The hydroxymercuri-derivatives of the substituted cyanoacetamides were prepared by the action of mercury acetamide on the cyanoacetamides in equimolecular proportion in presence of alcohol.

Hydroxymercuricyanacetmethylamide.—Cyanacetmethylamide (2 g.) dissolved in alcohol, was heated to boiling and a hot solution of mercury acetamide (6.5 g.) in alcohol was added. A snow white flocculent precipitate immediately appeared which settled down in the course of about twelve hours. The precipitate was washed with alcohol and then with distilled water several times in order to remove any unchanged reactants. The product is insoluble in most organic solvents. It begins to turn brown at 287° but does not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 63.98 ; N, 8.74. $C_4H_6O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 63.69 ; N, 8.90 per cent.).

Action of Potassium Iodide.—0.127 G. of the above compound was suspended in water and about one g. of potassium iodide was added. The mixture was refluxed on a sand-bath for four hours and the liberated alkali was titrated against 0.0174N-hydrochloric acid of which 44.7 c.c. were required. This shows the presence of 1.923 equivalents of alkali indicating that the splitting of the C—Hg linkage is almost quantitative.

Action of Hydrochloric Acid.—The above mercury compound is slowly decomposed by 0.25N-hydrochloric acid (hot) giving the original amide and mercuric chloride.

Action of Phenylhydrazine.—About 1 g. of the mercury compound was treated with 2 c.c. of phenylhydrazine. A vigorous reaction ensued in the cold and effervescence due to liberated nitrogen was observed. A grey precipitate of metallic mercury was formed which quickly collected and settled at the bottom of the flask. The mixture was then diluted with water and filtered. The solution on concentration and cooling deposited shining needles of pure cyanacetmethylamide, m.p. 101°.

Hydroxymercuricyanacetethylamide.—This was prepared from 1 g. of cyanacetethylamide and 2.9 g. of mercury acetamide. It does not melt till 300° but turns brown above 285°. (Found: Hg, 60.70 ; N, 8.76. $C_5H_8O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 60.98 ; N, 8.54 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-n-propylamide was prepared from equimolecular quantities of cyanacet-n-propylamide and mercury acetamide in presence of alcohol. It begins to turn brown above 265° and melts with decomposition at 280°. (Found: Hg, 58.24 ; N, 8.42. $C_6H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 58.48 ; N, 8.19 per cent.).

Preparation of Cyanacet-n-butylamide.—In the preparation of the alkyl amides of cyanacetic ester the method of Bakes, West and Whitely (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119. 367) was employed, Ethyl

cyanoacetate (10 g.) and *n*-butylamine (6.5 g.) were mixed up in a sealed tube which was kept for twenty-four hours and then heated at 125° for six hours. After cooling the red crystalline mass was washed with petroleum and crystallised from benzene—petroleum mixture when it separated in the form of white slender needles, m.p. 73°. It is very soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, and toluene but sparingly in petroleum. (Found: N, 20.26. $C_7H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 20.00 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-n-butylamide.—Prepared from cyanacet-*n*-butylamide and mercury acetamide in the usual manner, it did not undergo any change till 300°. (Found: Hg, 55.88; N, 8.12. $C_7H_{12}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 56.18; N, 7.87 per cent.).

Preparation of Cyanacetisobutylamide.—Ethyl cyanoacetate (10g.) and isobutylamine (6.5 g.) were condensed in the usual way. The mixture on strong cooling solidified. It was purified by crystallisation from hot water (charcoal). It is very soluble in all the organic solvents, and melts at 45°. (Found: N, 20.06. $C_7H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 20.00 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacetisobutylamide turns brown above 280° but does not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 56.43; N, 7.72. $C_7H_{12}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 56.18; N, 7.87 per cent.).

Preparation of Cyanacet-n-amylamide.—Ethyl cyanoacetate and *n*-amylamine were condensed in the usual manner. The product was crystallised from benzene—petroleum mixture after purifying it with bone charcoal. It formed feathery needles, m.p. 47°. (Found: N, 18.00. $C_8H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 18.18 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-n-amylamide melts with decomposition at 285°. (Found: Hg, 54.40; N, 7.43. $C_8H_{14}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 54.06; N, 7.57 per cent.).

Preparation of Cyanacetisohexylamide.—Ethyl cyanoacetate (10 g.) and isohexylamine (9 g.) were condensed in the usual manner. The product is very soluble in alcohol, benzene, etc. It was crystallised from water as slender, colourless needles, m.p. 42°. (Found: N, 16.92. $C_9H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 16.66 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacetisohexylamide melts with decomposition at 273°. (Found: Hg, 51.96; N, 7.08. $C_9H_{16}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 52.09; N, 7.29 per cent.).

Preparation of Cyanacet-n-heptylamide.—This was prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (10 g.) and *n*-heptylamine (10 g.) in the usual manner. It is very soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, and

benzene and sparingly in ether and petroleum. It separates from benzene—petroleum mixture in the form of fine, colourless needles melting at 67°. (Found: N, 15.20. $C_{10}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 15.38 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-n-heptylamide was prepared as usual from cyanacet-n-heptylamide and mercury acetamide. It turns brown at 270° and melts at 284°. (Found: Hg, 49.81; N, 6.99. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 50.25; N, 7.04 per cent.).

Ethyl Hydroxymercuricyanoacetate.—Ethyl cyanoacetate was treated with the calculated quantity of mercury acetamide in alcoholic solution. The product is insoluble in most of the ordinary organic solvents and does not suffer any change till 300°. (Found: Hg, 61.08; N, 4.37. $C_5H_7O_3NHg$ requires Hg, 60.79; N, 4.25 per cent.).

Action of Potassium Iodide.—0.1484 G. of ethyl hydroxymercuricyanoacetate was suspended in water and about 1 g. of potassium iodide was added. The mixture was refluxed for four hours and the liberated alkali was titrated against 0.0174N-hydrochloric acid (50.9 c.c.). This shows the presence of 1.96 equivalents of alkali, indicating the complete rupture of the C—Hg linkage.

Hydroxymercuricyanoacetamide was prepared from equimolecular quantities of cyanoacetamide and mercury acetamide in aqueous solution. It does not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 66.24; N, 9.70. $C_3H_4O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 66.66; N, 9.33 per cent.).

Action of Bromine.—Aqueous bromine was slowly added to a suspension of the above compound in water, till it was no longer absorbed. The flask was finally heated on a water-bath for about half an hour. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue was extracted with benzene. On cooling the benzene extract, small needles separated out which, on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 126°. It is identical with dibromocyanoacetamide.

The mercury derivatives of the substituted cyanoacetamides containing aromatic nuclei were similarly prepared by mixing equimolecular quantities of the amides and mercury acetamide in hot alcoholic solution.

Hydroxymercuricyanacetanilide does not undergo any change till 300°. (Found: Hg, 53.48; N, 7.22. $C_9H_8O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 53.19; N, 7.45 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid.—The above compound was treated with 25 c.c. of 0.25N-hydrochloric acid. On heating, a clear solution was obtained which on cooling deposited small needles which

were collected and on purification proved to be cyanacetanilide, m. p. 199°.

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-m-toluidide does not undergo any change till 300°. (Found: Hg, 51·70 ; N, 7·23. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 51·28 ; N, 7·18 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-o-toluidide does not melt below 300°. (Found: Hg, 50·94. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 51·28 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-p-toluidide does not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 50·90. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 51·28 per cent.)

Hydroxymercuricyanacetbenzylamide melts with decomposition at 293°. (Found: Hg, 55·98. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 51·28 per cent.).

Action of Bromine.—The above compound was treated with bromine till it was no longer absorbed. The flask was heated on a water-bath for about 15 mins. when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling, the solution deposited light, white tufts, which after recrystallisation from benzene melted at 92°. (Found: Br, 31·44. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2Br$ requires Br, 31·62 per cent.).

Reduction of the Bromo-derivative.—0·138 G. of the substance liberated iodine equivalent to 54·6 c.c. of 0·02N-sodium thiosulphate. (Found: Br, 31·65. Calc. Br(labile), 31·62 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet- α -naphthylamide turns grey at 253° and melts with decomposition at 272°. (Found: Hg, 47·23. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 46·95 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet- β -naphthylamide melts with decomposition at 283°. (Found: Hg, 46·71. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 46·95 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-1:3:4-xylidide does not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 50·00. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 49·51 per cent.).

Hydroxymercuricyanacet-1:4:5-xylidide does not undergo any change till 300°. (Found: Hg, 49·87. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 49·51 per cent.).

The authors take this opportunity to express their gratitude to the Government of his Highness the Gaekwar of Baroda for a grant which has defrayed the expenses incurred in this work.

